

Synthesis of Δ^1 and Δ^2 -cyclopentene-1.2-dicarboxylic Acids

BY BIRENDRA LAL NANDI.

cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (IV) was first prepared by Hawarth and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 978) from saturated *cyclopentane acid*. Willstätter prepared the same acid (*Ber.*, 1895, 26, 663) by cyclising ethyl $\alpha\alpha'$ -dibromopimelate by means of sodium ethoxide and then hydrolysing the resultant cyclic unsaturated ester. Both the authors recorded the m.p. of the acid as 178° and they could not trace the presence of any isomeric acid. Hassell and Ingold, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1465) however, during the formation of ring compounds from straight chain bromo acids, isolated two isomeric *cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acids*, m.p. 178° and 146° respectively from cyclisation of ethyl $\alpha\alpha'$ -dibromopimelate. The present author, while studying the tautomeric capacity of unsaturated cyclic dicarboxylic acids under various conditions, found that both Perkin and Willstatter's methods gave rise to two isomeric acids namely the Δ^1 - and Δ^2 -*cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acids*.

A rational synthesis of both the acids has been accomplished. Ethyl *cyclopentane-1-one-2-carboxylate* (I) obtained by cyclising ethyl adipate was converted into the nitrile (II) by means of HCN which on dehydration with thionyl chloride and pyridine gave the unsaturated cyano-ester (III). The latter, on alkaline hydrolysis, gave rise to a mixture of Δ^1 - and Δ^2 -*cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acids* (IV) and (V) (*cf. Kon and Nandi, J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1628.)

The constitution of the two isomeric acids has been confirmed by ozonisation. The ozonised product of ethyl ester of Δ^1 -acid gave diphenylhydrazone of ethyl $\alpha\alpha'$ -diketopimelate, m.p. 147° (Blaise and Gault, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1862, i, 4, 81). The ozonised product of the Δ^2 -acid, after decomposition of the ozonide and subsequent treatment with hydrogen peroxide, gave glutaric acid.

The two isomeric unsaturated acids were isolated by fractional crystallisation from ethyl acetate and water, the Δ^1 -acid separating first. Both the acids on equilibrations under standard conditions of Linstead and May (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 353, 362) gave rise to a mixture of the two isomeric acids of indefinite melting point. Unfortunately it was impossible to follow the interconversion because iodometric and bromometric methods of estimations of the two isomerides failed, since they had almost equal bromine additions (70% and 74% respectively) and iodine did not react with them at all. The barium and other suitable inorganic salt methods (Kon and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2439) also failed since the barium, cadmium salts, etc., of both the isomeric acids are soluble in water.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl cyclopentane 1-one-2-carboxylate was prepared by cyclising ethyl adipate (284 g.) in presence of molecular sodium (35 g.) in benzene, yield 80 %; b. p. $106-109^\circ/12$ mm.

Ethyl cyclopentane-1-hydroxy-1-cyano-2-carboxylate.—To the above keto-ester (90 g.) was added potassium cyanide (100 g., 95% s.s.) in 20 % solution. The flask was fitted with a dropping funnel and a leadway for hydrocyanic acid. To the ice-cold solution was run in strong hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.) drop by drop with constant shaking (1 hour) and the whole left overnight at room temperature. The ester was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed once with dilute sodium carbonate solution, then with water, dried and the ether removed.

The residue was distilled with a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid, b.p. $143^\circ/10$ mm., yield 85%. (Found: C, 58.9; H, 7.0; N, 7.58. $C_9H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 59.0; H, 7.1; N, 7.6 per cent).

Ethyl cyclopentene-1-cyano-2-carboxylate.—Attempts were made to dehydrate the above cyanhydrin with different dehydrating agents and thionyl chloride in presence of pyridine was found to be the best. The cyanhydrin (74 g.) was mixed with pyridine (56 g.) and cooled in a freezing mixture. Thionyl chloride (40 g.) was added with

constant shaking in the course of half an hour and the flask was kept in the freezing mixture for another 2 hours and then at room temperature for 6 hours. Ice-cold water was added and the liquid extracted with ether; the ethereal solution was washed thoroughly with caustic soda solution (10%) till it was decolourised; it was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, water, then dried and the ether removed. The unsaturated ester distilled at $132^{\circ}/11$ mm., yield 41%. (Found: C, 65.3; H, 6.6; N, 8.3. $C_9H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 65.4; H, 6.7; N, 8.5 per cent).

Δ^1 - and Δ^2 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acids.—Ethyl cyclopentene-1-cyano-2-carboxylate (8 g.) was hydrolysed with 22% caustic potash solution (10 g.) under a condenser sufficiently short to permit the escape of alcohol vapour. After acidification the mixed isomeric acids were extracted with ether in a continuous extractor, m.p. $140-50^{\circ}$, yield 7.4 g. By repeated crystallisation of this impure acid from water 2.1 g. of Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid were isolated, m.p. and mixed m.p. with Perkin's acid 178° . (Found: C, 53.8; H, 5.0. $C_7H_8O_4$ requires C, 53.9; H, 5.1 per cent).

The mother liquor was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the isomeric acid was purified by alternate crystallisation from water and ethyl acetate, m.p. 146° . (Found: C, 53.7; H, 5.0 per cent).

Oxidation of ethyl Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylate.—The pure Δ^1 -acid was esterified *via* silver salt, b.p. $140^{\circ}/16$ mm. d_4^{20} , 1.0805; n_D^{20} , 1.4652; $(R_L)_D$, 54.26. (Found: C, 62.3; H, 7.3. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 62.3; H, 7.5 per cent).

The pure ester (7 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (100 c.c.) and a current of ozone was passed till absorption was complete (20 hrs.). After removal of the solvent at reduced pressure and decomposition of the ozonide by shaking with water (12 hrs.) and extracting with ether the residue gave the phenylhydrazone of ethyl $\alpha\alpha'$ -diketo adipate from acetone melting at 147° . (Found: C, 64.9; H, 6.6. $C_{23}H_{28}O_4N_4$ requires C, 65.1; H, 6.6 per cent). That the oxidation product was ethyl $\alpha\alpha'$ -diketo adipate was further proved by hydrolysis and subsequent oxidation by hydrogen peroxide to glutaric acid (m.p. and mixed m.p. with glutaric acid 97°).

Oxidation of Δ^2 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid.—The pure Δ^2 -acid (5 g.) was dissolved in dilute sodium carbonate solution (a little over theoretical) and a rapid stream of ozone was passed into it till absorption was complete (8 hrs.). After decomposition of the

ozonide by shaking, the product was extracted with ether after acidification. The residue after removal of ether did not give any phenylhydrazone. It was next dissolved in dilute caustic potash solution and treated with hydrogen peroxide (10 vol, 20 c.c.) and left overnight, acidified and again extracted with ether in a continuous extractor. 4.4 G. of a solid was isolated which when crystallised twice from ethyl acetate gave m.p. and mixed m.p. with glutaric acid, 97°.

Equilibrations.—Both the pure isomeric cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acids (1 g.) were dissolved in the required amount (11 equivalents of a 25% solution by wt.) of caustic potash solution and heated for one hour in a closed tube in boiling water. After cooling the product was acidified with 19% hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether in a continuous extractor. In both the cases a mixture of acids was obtained melting indefinitely at 140-50° from which both Δ^1 - and Δ^2 -acids were separated by alternate crystallisation from ethyl acetate and water as stated above.

Under standard conditions of Linstead and May (*loc. cit.*) both Δ^1 -acid and its isomeride gave almost instantaneous bromine additions (70% and 74% respectively of the theoretical amount in 10 minutes), while iodine did not react with them at all.

The barium, calcium, strontium and cadmium salts of both the isomeric acids are soluble in water.